

Content Analysis and Attitude of Thai Students towards Thai Series “Hormones: Season 2”

Siriporn Meenan

Abstract—The objective of this study is to investigate the attitude of Thai students towards the Thai series "Hormones the Series Season 2". This study was conducted in the quantitative research, and the questionnaires were used to collect data from 400 people of the sample group. Descriptive statistics were used in data analysis. The findings reveal that most participants have positive comments regarding the series. They strongly agreed that the series reflects on the way of life and problems of teenagers in Thailand. Hence, the participants believe that if adults have a chance to watch the series, they will have the better understanding of the teenagers. In addition, the participants also agreed that the contents of the play are appropriate and satisfiable as the contents of “Hormones the Series Season 2” will raise awareness among the teens and use it as a guide to prevent problems that might happen during their teenage life.

Keywords—Content analysis, attitude, Thai series, Hormones the series.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE series Hormones is a Thai teen drama television series produced by GTH and Nadao Bangkok. The show follows the lives of a group of secondary school students (Grade 11) as they go through school and home life and face various issues.

The series' first season was positively received and extensively discussed among Thai society. The series' first season was directed by Songyos Sugmakanan, consisting of 15 episodes and was broadcast on satellite channel GMM One and online from May to August 2013. The series was positively received and, despite not being shown on free-to-air terrestrial television and being criticized for its content, proved extremely popular, prompting the creation of a second season. Directed by Kriangkrai Vachiratamporn, the second season began broadcasting in July 2014.

At the first time, GTH originally planned for only one season, but at the end of the first season, GTH announced that it would be producing a second one, responding to the show's popularity. Songyos, the director of the first season, switched roles to become a producer for the second season, with Kriangkrai Vachiratamporn, who had co-written the series, becoming a director. GTH also launched a casting program with an accompanying reality series titled Hormones: The Next Gen, in order to select additional actors to supplement the original main cast from the first season.

The series' second season began in July 2014. However, it was switched to another GMM Grammy-owned channel, GTH On Air, which is available only through Grammy's own GMM

Z set-top box. Although YouTube live streaming was still offered to the season's past episodes. responding to viewer's complaints, GTH later offered a simulcast on GMM Channel, a digital terrestrial channel.

Due to the internet and the new media, Hormones also received tremendous response from audiences outside Thailand like Vietnam, The Philippines, Indonesia and China. In China, Hormones has a huge base of fans that watch the fansub version of this series on various video streaming sites.

This incident reflects the competition of contents. It indicates the readiness of the producers or owners of satellite TV stations to compete against the traditional free TV stations. With these contents and audience base that already exists, satellite TV stations have built its success to Digital TV. This is the challenge for the television industry in Thailand. Despite the broadcast channels, it can be successful if the content is good. Free TV stations are challenged by the satellite TV that is turning to digital TV. Moreover, agencies and product owners can select to advertise to better meet their target groups from increasing number and variety of media. However, Hormones the series Season 2 has been criticized by the society that the content is inappropriate especially the sexual content that is communicated. This reflects that the current situation in Thailand has faced many challenges among the developments in the social, economic, and cultural dimensions. The major challenge that is needed to be realized is the sexual communication. As the Thai Society has determined the ideas and beliefs that sexual is prohibited and should not be discussed in public. The impact of this mind concept has raised many problems about sex. For example, sexual abuse, sexual violence, gender bias, transmitted sexual disease, and the curiosity of people in Thai society about sex [1]. Nevertheless, such ideas often come from adults. Therefore, the researcher is interested in the opinion of the real target group of this series that is teens. The researcher is studying on “the content analysis and attitudes of Thai student towards Thai series: Hormones the series Season 2” in use as a guide the better knowledge and understanding in Sexual Education and the appropriate ways to communicate the sexual issues through media in the future.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the study of “Content Analysis and Attitude of Thai Student toward Thai Series: Hormones the Series Season 2”, the researcher has reviewed the concepts, frameworks, and theories to adapt use in approaching the studies. All literature reviews can be classified into the following sub-topics.

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A. Information Seeking Theory

As for the information seeking, when a person takes action to seek for the information to meet his needs, to gain knowledge, study, and analyze on topics. If a person found that the information is insufficient, he will study on the topic further by seeking more information [2].

When a person is selecting the information from the media, it is up to the comparison between Reward Value, Expenditures, and Liabilities that will follow. For example, if the reward value of receiving information or entertainment is higher than the expenditures i.e. the cost of getting the information or efforts made to get and understand the information, it is considered as Information Seeking. However, if the expenditures are more than the information received, it is considered as Information Yielding where the person receives the information reluctantly. Information yielding, for instance, when we would watch the TV advertisements over and over because we are too tired to change the channel or we will see the same old advertisements across the channels. We are forced to watch them when we do not want to. Moreover, [3] suggested that seeking information and the media needs of the individual is to receive the information and entertainment. The information needs arise from ignorance and uncertainty of the individual that are the following factors: First, Inconsistencies between the knowledge of the individual and the needs to know about the external environment (Extrinsic Uncertainty). More important information causes higher the curiosity. Inconsistencies between the existing knowledge of the individual and the desired level of knowledge which is determined by the level of the individual's interest (Intrinsic Uncertainty).

For the individual needs of entertainment that are aroused by the festive mood which came from the inconsistencies between the individual's living conditions and the desired level of joy (Intrinsic Desire).

The information that can reduce the ignorance and uncertainty of the individual (Intrinsic Uncertainty) and is associated with the individual joy (Immediate Consummately Gratifications). For the information that can reduce the ignorance associated with the external environment (Extrinsic Uncertainty), Atkin [4] believe that some information can be used as a tool to generate information ideas and solve problems (Instrumental Utilities) in daily life, and at the same time, provide the entertainment.

In conclusion, not only the objective of seeking information is to support the existing ideas, attitude, and understanding, seeking information can also be used to gather knowledge, and as guidelines to problem-solving. Furthermore, it helps to satisfy the individual's interest and entertainment. Nevertheless, the decision of seeking or ignoring the information depends on the individual's evaluation of the Reward Value of the information that the audience is received.

B. Uses and Gratification Theory

The theory about the use and satisfaction of the media or to use the media for the benefit and satisfaction is the theory that emphasizes on the media audience by emphasizing that the

audience is the driving mechanisms in selecting the type of media to meet their needs. As the communicator, this indicates the importance of the audience as the audience is not only influenced by the media only.

The attitude of the Passive Person will be changed according to the effect of the media. However, the active person will have the desire to choose the media to meet their needs. This theory has assumed that human knows that the information they received can be used for their benefit.

Katz and others [4] studied the data collected from the media user in Israel. The study is to research and finding the tools to measure the use and satisfaction of media rather than testing the assumption. Therefore, Katz and Other [4] created a tool to measure psychological and human social needs by bringing together the three following components: First, Mode is the nature of needs. For instance, increasing and reducing of needs and the needs of getting the information. Second, Connection is the objective of connecting the individual with external environment i.e. the connection to receive the information and knowledge, to meet satisfaction, to gain emotional experience, to ensure the beliefs, confidence, stability, status, and the connection of relationships. Third, Referent is the individual or external environment that the humans are linked to which include self, family, friends, social, government, tradition, culture, world, and other negative effects.

The model that [4] created explains social and psychological differences that caused the different human needs to receive the different level of satisfaction from using the media. This model shows the case that an individual has the basic social and psychological needs.

Kippax and Murry [5] used the idea of Katz [4] to study. In addition to focusing on the use of media, the objective of this study is to find the relationship of the needs for the use of media and the satisfaction, and the use and benefit of media. The study found the following: First, the individual factor such as gender, age, education, and occupation determines the use and perceives the benefits of media. Especially the age factor, the study [4] found that the sample or age group 9 to 11 and younger uses the media for entertainment while the older age group uses media to receive the information about social and their own needs. Second, People with higher population are using media more than the lower education. Third, From the types of media that are used to study, television has the most audience uses as the target group finds that televisions have many types of information such as the world, the situation in our country, and also, the entertainment while newspaper, magazine, radio, and movies follow. Fourth, most of the target group select media with purpose and understand the value of media.

Kippax and Murray's study concludes that the needs of media are in relation to the learning of benefits of the media and the individual factors that influence the choice of media.

In addition, [6], on the news gratifications, has divided the consumer satisfactions into four following groups: First, Orientation Gratifications is the use of information to be used as references, to support the relationship between individual

and social, and the type of needs that will follow such as the Information Surveillance, or receiving information to be used as Decisional Utility. Second, Social Gratifications is to use the information as the linkage between the information relating to social's perception and the individual's network such as to use the information in the conversations or to persuade others. Third, Para-Social Gratifications refers to the process to use the information to establish the individual's identity or to reference a person that involves or appears in the media. Fourth, Para-Orientation Gratifications refers to the process to reduce and ease the stress or to protect individual self, such as to use the media as entertainment to get away from other dissatisfaction.

C.A Concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

A concept of responsibility on the media distribution was initiated in 1947 in the United States. A commission on the freedom of the press has prepared a report which clearly shown in the report that, although freedom of the press is to be confirmed the following have identified key practices that the media are responsible for any action [7]. First, the media must reflect the actual side of the incident that happened in the social. And they have to be careful in examining the information without the context of the event has occurred. Second, the media presented must create a platform for representation and exchange of public opinion. Third, the press has a responsibility to represent the voice of the society and also presented the goals and values of social advantage.

Karnchana Kaewdevi has presented her work to identified the key characteristics of social responsibility theory of the press into four points. First, the media must conduct a mission to society media should be in public ownership. Second, the media will be truthful, accurate, fair, straightforward and consistent. Third, the media have served as a platform to share the different ideas. Fourth, the media should be conducted according to ethical principles and standards of the profession. And in some situations, Society may require intervention to the interests of the media.

Harold Lass well (1948) [8], an American political scientist refers to the role of the media in the book called "The Structure and Function of Communication" as three responsible functions. First, work as a surveillance of the environment. Second, work correlates with the different part of society in responding to the environment. The third reason is to be a transmission of social heritage from one generation the next generation. Besides, Schramm and Write (1975) [9] added on the fourth of press responsibility, which is the function of entertainment which means to publish Thai arts and musical performances into arts of living for the local people.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is from the content analysis and survey of attitudes of teen towards, the series Hormones Season 2 by using the quantitative research methodology. The questionnaire is used as a tool to collect the data from the sample. The samples are 400 teenagers in Bangkok who have

watched the series Hormones Season 2.

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics which will be divided into the following parts:

Part 1 and Part 2 are the general analysis and viewing habits of the series Hormones Season 2 that were analyzed by frequency and percentage.

Part 3 analyzes the data about the attitudes of an audience of the series Hormones Season 2 based on the Likert Scale. The scales are divided into 5 levels (1-5) which are Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Uncertain, Agree, and Strongly Agree respectively.

The scores obtained are weighted to determine the audience's level of feedback. The weighted scores are divided into 5 levels which are Most Strongly Agree (scoring 4.50-5.00), Strongly Agree (scoring 3.50-4.49), Moderately Agree (scoring 2.50-3.49), Less Agree (scoring 1.50-2.49), and Least Agree (scoring 1.00-1.49).

IV. FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The survey of the sample consisted of 400 respondents found that most of the respondents are female. The respondents are in the age range of 14-22 which is the age range that is currently enrolled in high school or undergraduate.

The study of viewing the behavior of the series Hormones Season 2 found that 60 percent watch every episode of the series, 30 percent often watch the series, and only 10 percent rarely watch the series. In addition, the study found that 56 percent pay attention to all scenes in the series, 20 percent only pay attention to the interesting scenes, 14 per cent watch the series to know what each episode is about, and 10 percent that does not pay attention to the content. The study also found that 35 percent of the sample watch the series for entertainment, 30 watch the series so that they will be able to communicate with others, and 27 percent watch the series to relax and 8 percent watch for other purposes such as using their free time, knowing the current trends in Thai society and the way of living of Thai teenagers.

On the attitude aspects, the study found that most of the samples have positive attitudes towards the Hormones Season 2 series as most of the topics in the questionnaire receive the Strongly Agree such as hormones reflects the way of life of teenagers in Thailand. Moreover, the series also best reflects problems of teenagers in Thailand, and the actors of this series played their roles impressively.

The topics that most of the sample has agreed is the interesting contents of the series. The sample is satisfied with the way the contents are presented, timing and duration of the broadcast. Moreover, the contents have raised the awareness among teenagers about the problems that might have happened during the teenage years. The contents appeared to be the guidelines to help the teenagers solve the problems that might happen. In addition, the study also found that the contents in the series are appropriate. However, most of the sample thinks that Thai teenagers may imitate the inappropriate behavior from the content of the series and is uncertain that this series is the appropriate series for all ages.

The research reflects that Thai teenagers have looked at the taboo differently now. From the traditional belief that these topics are inappropriate to be spoken in public or through media, the topics has been transformed to appropriate and should be spoken in the straight manner to reflect the current situation in Thai society by hoping that the media will be another channel to communicate these topics to others. Especially for the adults, to have the better understanding of teens way of living and what they are currently facing.

As the professional press that has ethics as guidelines, the media should be careful in presenting these taboos especially if the target group are teenagers who are still a lack of maturity or lack of suppressiveness. The contents presentation without careful consideration might raise to the inappropriate behavior if the target group is unable to perceive what the media is trying to present.

For the suggestion, the next research should use the focus group and in-depth interview to gather the in-depth information on the perspective of teenagers on the soap-opera or show that have controversial issues on the appropriateness of the content. Moreover, the research should be on media literacy of teenagers to be used as the decision factor for the media what wants to produce the contents that have teenagers as a target group. In addition, it can be used as evidence to indicate the level of awareness of the media on the overall social impact to be according to the aspirations of careers in journalism.

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